

ACID: **A**strophysical **C**ircles **D**etector

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Astrophysical Circles Detector (ACID)

- General purpose “astrophysical circles” detector.

Raw image

ACID detections

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Boulders on 67P/C-G

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Raw image

Acid detections

Cyclones on Jupiter

Astrophysical Circles Detector (ACID)

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Over/under densities in galaxies
Maccio, Ali-Dib et al. (2022) MNRAS.

Astrophysical Craters Detector (ACID)

- **General purpose craters detector.**
- **Built on the MaskRCNN neural network (Ali-Dib et al. 2020)**
- **Trained on a massive craters (only) dataset**
- **Available now at github.com/malidib/ACID**
- **Paper on arxiv soon.**